

IMPACT OF SCHOOL LOCATION ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL PRINCIPALS IN ENUGU STATE

Rev. Fr. Dr. Onubuleze Franklin Kelechi

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education. Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT) Enugu, Nigeria.

Abstract: *The study determined the impact of school location on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. In this study, the researcher adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was 8,813 respondents. It comprised 293 principals and 8,522 teachers in Enugu State owned secondary schools. The sample for this study was 285. The researcher used a proportionate sampling technique to obtain the sample size. Hence, the sample size comprised 29 principals, which was 10% of the principals' population as well as 256 teachers, which was 3% of the teachers' population. The instrument for data collection was a researcher developed questionnaire titled "Impact of School Location on Principals' Effectiveness Questionnaire (ISLPEQ)". The instrument was validated by three research experts in the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha in which 0.78 was gotten for section A and 0.81 for section B with an overall reliability index of 0.80, which made the instrument reliable. The researcher administered the 285 copies of the questionnaire with the help of two research assistants. Data analysis was done using mean and standard deviation and hypotheses tested using a t-test. A 4 point response scale of Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) was used. The findings of the study revealed that physical facilities have an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State to a great extent. Also, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which physical facilities have an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that the educational administrators and planners who prepare the budget for the procurement of physical facilities should increase the budget to ensure that secondary schools are stocked with physical facilities that are adequate in quantity and in quality.*

Keywords: School Location, Principals, Effectiveness, Physical Facilities, School Plant planning

Introduction

A school is one of the institutions that is responsible for the development and training of the mind and skill of man. Oredein, (2016), defined a school as a social and learning agent that provides the environment upon which a child may be formally educated in order to attain educational goals. School is a formal organization which serves as a transitional stage in life between family and the society (Olabode, 2012). The school is a factor of tremendous importance in education (Anbalangan, 2017).

Secondary education is critical to the education of a child, being the bridge between primary and higher institutions (Ige, 2011). The effort made by the teachers can actualize the programmes of the secondary education. A teacher is one who teaches the young ones, builds up, instructs, trains and guides them for healthy

growth and stable adult life (Majasan in Akpakwu, Olaitan and Sanusi, 2014). Anbalangan, (2017) stated that the location of a school is critical in the actualization of set standard of secondary education..

School location is referred to as the community in which the school is located, such as a village, hamlet or rural area. School location refers to the particular place, in relation to other areas in the physical environment (rural or urban), where the school is sited (Ntibi & Edoho, 2017). According to Okorie & Ezeh (2016), school location is referred to as the particular place, in relation to other areas in the physical environment (rural or urban), where the school is sited. Bello and Ezeh in Eze (2010) opined that school location is known to influence students' learning through quality of teaching staff, class size and availability of infrastructure. Rural-urban location has been found all over the world to be an important indicator or difference in performance both for teachers and students' academic outcomes. Adewale (2012) posited that the location of school has an impact on the learning activities of the secondary school students. Nsa, Offiong, Udo & Ikot (2014), stated that school location variables that affect teaching and learning include the following: Science and Computer laboratories, library facilities, adequate classroom facilities, workshop facilities, farm buildings and structures, farm lands and play grounds among others. The school location must be inviting or welcoming, conducive and accommodating for adequate and effective learning to take place.

Effectiveness is the degree to which an organization approximates to achieving its goals. Effectiveness is the ability to plan, organize and coordinate many and often-conflicting social energies in a single organization so adroitly (Besong, 2014). Olaitan in Nwosu (2010) defined effectiveness as knowledge, skills, attitudes, and judgment generally required for the successful performance of a task. The success of any organisation like the secondary education largely depends on principals' effectiveness.

Principals are the chief executive officers of the secondary schools. Egwu (2016) defined a principal as a leader who must plan, coordinate and supervise the affairs of the school so that they run smoothly. Principals' effectiveness is based on the way a principal runs the school in an easy and effective manner. It is the positive response to administrative efforts and actions with the intention to accomplish stated goal (Akomolafe & Ademilua, 2012). The location of a school has a big role to play on the effectiveness of principals in the school. Mhishi, Erinosa and Sana (2012) reported that most principals working in rural areas find themselves disadvantaged compared to their urban area counterparts. Mhishi, Erinosa and Sana, (2012) further reported that teachers in most secondary schools have no access to facilities such as libraries, good housing, banking, clean tap water, Internet services and electricity. Lack of these basic amenities have made most rural school principals frustrated and are now concentrating more in improving their living conditions in the rural areas at the expense of diligently discharging their duties thus concerning performance in school. In this, the researcher focused on school location variables like physical facilities and school plant planning in order to determine their impacts on the effectiveness of secondary school principals.

Physical facilities refer to the buildings, playgrounds and mobile structures provided for the purpose of enhancing teaching and learning process. Oshahem in Onwe (2015) referred to school physical facilities as tangible structures, which serve educational purposes. Physical facilities are buildings and grounds, parking lots, playing fields, and fixed equipment. Physical facilities have been observed as a potent factor to qualitative education (Owoeye, 2011). An effective physical facility is responsive to the changing programmes of educational delivery, and at a minimum should provide a physical environment that is comfortable, safe, secure, accessible, well illuminated, well ventilated, and aesthetically pleasing (Adesua, 2016). Physical facilities are

expected to be adequately provided to create a favourable environment for learning. Physical facilities and equipment are essential to get schoolwork done.

Another aspect of school location is school plant planning. School plant refer to non-human and non-financial resources (Olagboye in Suleman & Gbolahan, 2017). Lawanson and Gede (2011) defined school plant as those things that enable the teacher to do his/her work very well and helping the learners to learn effectively. School plant planning is the basic concept behind educational facilities planning. School plant planning such as school site planning instructional space planning, administrative space planning circulation space planning and space of convenience planning are essential in teaching and learning process (Irele in Musibau, Abiodun & Abayomi, 2016).

The success of every student lies on the nature of activities of the school. The poor standard of physical facilities as well as lack of proper school plant planning like the absence of ceiling, chairs, desks for students, inadequate teaching personnel and support staff, makes the principals ineffective in the course of performing their duties. Based on the above assertions, the researcher sought to investigate the impact of school location on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

There have been a series of reports by parents, stakeholders and the society at large about the state of facilities in state owned secondary schools, especially in Enugu State. Critical secondary education stakeholders have a complaint that there is inadequate ventilation and lighting in schools, classrooms are located very close to technical workshops, industries and main road. There are inadequacies of instructional resources; even the available ones are not properly utilized by the school teachers because some of them are obsolete. These inadequacies do not make teaching and learning conducive, hence, the effectiveness of secondary school principals may not be guaranteed.

Sequel to the above assertion, it therefore, presupposes that school location variables like physical facilities and school plant planning must never be overlooked. This is because they are the pedestal on which effective learning outcomes rest. This, therefore, constitutes the worries of this researcher. The problem of this study when put in question form, is therefore, “what is the impact of school location on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State”?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the impact of school location on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the impact of school location on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State in terms of physical facilities;
2. identify the impact of school location on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State as regards school plant planning.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent to which physical facilities have an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State?
2. What is the extent to which school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study:

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

Research Method

In this study, the researcher adopted a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research design, according to Nworgu (2015) is referred to as the design that aims at collecting data and describing them systematically. This design is appropriate for this study in that the researcher used a sample from secondary school principals and teachers, who were considered to be representative of the population. The study was conducted in Enugu State. The population for the study was 8,813 respondents. It comprised 293 principals and 8,522 teachers in Enugu State owned secondary schools. The sample for this study was 285. The researcher used proportionate sampling technique to obtain the sample size. Hence, the sample size comprised 29 principals which was 10% of the principals’ population as well as 256 teachers which was 3% of the teachers’ population. This is in agreement with Uzoagulu (2011) who posited that if the population for a study is known and it is made up of different groups, each group received allocation based on its proportion to the population. Uzoagulu also posited that no fixed number and percentage is ideal for drawing a sample rather it is the circumstance of the study situation that determines what percentage of the population should be used.

The instrument for data collection was a researcher developed questionnaire titled “Impact of School Location on Principals’ Effectiveness Questionnaire (ISLPEQ)”. The instrument was validated by three research experts in the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). Two of the research experts were from the Department of Educational Management while one was from measurement and Evaluation unit of the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha in which 0.78 was gotten for section A and 0.81 for section B with an overall reliability index of 0.80 which made the instrument reliable. The researcher administered the 285 copies of questionnaire with the help of two research assistants. At the end of the exercise, they retrieved 261 copies (21 from principals and 240 from teachers) making it a 91.58% return rate. Data analysis was done using mean and standard deviation and hypotheses tested using t-test. A 4 point response scale of Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) was used. The decision was that hypothesis was not significant when the t-calculated value was less than the table value, but significant when the t-calculated value was greater than the critical table value.

Research Question 1: What is the extent to which physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State

ITEMS		Principals 21			Teachers 240		
S/N	The following physical facilities impact principals’ effectiveness by:	\bar{x}	SD	Dec.	\bar{x}	SD	Dec.

1	the availability of well equipped laboratories.	2.55	.90	GE	2.74	.90	GE
2	having a functional library service.	2.58	.95	GE	2.65	.95	GE
3	having adequate instructional materials in the school.	2.65	.97	GE	2.64	.89	GE
4	the availability of conducive staff rooms for teachers.	2.60	.95	GE	2.60	.95	GE
5	having adequate health facilities.	2.66	.90	GE	2.65	.91	GE
Cluster Mean		2.61	.93	GE	2.66	.92	GE

Data presented on Table 1 show that the responses of the respondents in items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were all to a great extent. The principals’ mean ranged from 2.55 to 2.66 that of teachers ranged from 2.60 to 2.74. In addition, they had cluster means of 2.61 and 2.66 for principals and teachers and standard deviations of .93 and .90 respectively. Thus, the finding revealed that physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State to a great extent.

Research Question 2: What is the extent to which school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State?

Table 2: Mean ratings of Principals and Teachers on the extent to which School Plant Planning has an impact on the Effectiveness of Secondary School Principals in Enugu State

ITEMS		Principals 21			Teachers 240		
S/N	School plant planning has an impact on principals’ effectiveness when:	\bar{x}	SD	Dec.	\bar{x}	SD	Dec.
6	the medical facilities are properly maintained.	2.61	.88	GE	2.58	.91	GE
7	the dilapidated buildings are renovated.	2.66	.91	GE	2.63	.93	GE
8	clean pipe born water is provided.	2.50	.91	GE	2.52	.87	GE
9	recreational facilities are in order.	2.59	.85	GE	2.60	.99	GE
10	adequate school buses are provided.	2.55	.99	GE	2.59	.88	GE
Cluster Mean		2.58	.91	GE	2.58	.92	GE

Data presented on Table 2 show that the responses of the respondents in items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 were all to a great extent. The principals’ mean ranged from 2.55 to 2.66 that of teachers ranged from 2.52 to 2.63. In addition, they had cluster means of 2.58 and 2.58 for principals and teachers and standard deviations of .91 and .92 respectively. This is an indication that school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State to a great extent.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

Table 3: t-test on the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State

Group	n	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Principals	21	2.61	.93	259	.24	1.96	Not Significant
Teachers	240	2.66	.92				

From the result of hypothesis 1 above, table 3 shows that the calculated value of .24 is less than the table value of 1.96 at 259 degree of freedom. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

Table 4: t-test on the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State

Group	n	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Principals	21	2.58	.91	259	.00	1.96	Not Significant
Teachers	240	2.58	.92				

From the result of hypothesis 2 above, table 4 shows that the calculated value of .00 is less than the table value of 1.96 at 259 degree of freedom. This signifies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study showed that physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals to a great extent. The evidence of the finding is based on the responses of the respondents. The finding is in accordance with Adaja & Osagie (2015) who stated that when there is adequate physical facilities in the school, the staff will perform their duties very well while the students’ academic performance will be improved, thereby, making the principals effective in the course of performing their duties. Further finding showed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which physical facilities have impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

The finding of the study revealed that school plant planning impacts the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State to a great extent. The finding is in correspondents with the view of Ajayi (2011) who maintained that school plant needs to be adequately planned in order to ensure effectiveness of the principals in the educational sector. Further finding showed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which school plant planning has an impact on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State.

Conclusions

The study ascertained the impact of school location on the effectiveness of secondary school principals in Enugu State. This study revealed the impact of school location in the aspect of adequacy of physical facilities and proper school plant planning on the effectiveness of secondary school principals. It established that school location has a significant impact on principals' effectiveness in the course of performing his duties.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. The educational administrators and planners who prepare the budget for the procurement of physical facilities should increase the budget to ensure that secondary schools are stocked with physical facilities that are adequate in quantity and in quality.
2. There should be constant maintenance of school plant in schools across the state in order to enhance principals' effectiveness.

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